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Exploring National Infrastructure for Public Access Usage and Impact Reporting

Date and Time: April 2, 2023; 8:00am - 4:00pm

Location: Sheraton Denver Downtown Hotel, Directors Row I

Overview

This workshop invites international experts and leading scholarly cyberinfrastructures to:

- a. identify challenges to cross-platform public and open impact analytics at scale,
- b. explore open infrastructure opportunities to improve the FAIRness of usage data, and
- c. identify what's needed to scaffold America's national infrastructure for scholarly output impact reporting in light of the Nelson memo and the European Open Science Cloud Core and Interoperability Framework.

Challenges related to public access impact reporting of data, articles, and books will be considered alongside anticipated issues related to complex, expansive, and emerging digital publications that may include simulations, 3D models, datasets, videos, and other multimedia. Workshop findings will be documented in a report that will be distributed through public repositories.

Objectives

- Identify what's needed to scaffold America's national infrastructure for scholarly output impact reporting.
- Develop recommendations for national infrastructure and investment.
- Prioritize and begin to map out what activities we need to undertake next to support these recommendations.

Prework

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pre-recorded 5-minute talks* 	<p>Collection of invited talks. <i>As you review the videos, please consider what common challenges exist in reporting the impact of public access to data, articles, and books and how we might address them.</i></p>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshop Summary 	<p>One page project summary. <i>This summarizes the aims for our workshop.</i></p>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Michael Clarke, Laura Ricci. "OA Books Supply Chain Mapping Report" (April 2021) 	<p>Research report. <i>As you review the report, consider how applicable the usage data supply chain and associated challenges are for scholarly outputs other than books.</i></p>	

*Thank you to our virtual speakers, who prepared invited talks to foster discussion and consideration despite being unable to join in person: Stefaan Verhulst ([NYU GovLab Data](#)); Tasha Mellins-Cohen ([COUNTER](#)); Jo Lambert (JISC/[IRUS-UK](#)); Paolo Manghi ([OpenAIRE / EOSC](#)); Greg Tananbaum ([Open Research Funders Group / HELIOS](#)), and Heather Madray (National Secure Data Service / [National Center for Science and Engineering Statistics](#)).

Agenda

07:45	Doors open - coffee / tea available
08:00-08:15	Welcome
08:15-09:00	Information sharing on existing efforts (5 minute talks) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Laura Ricci (Clarke&Esposito) • Niels Stern (OAPEN, EU and European Digital Infrastructure Collaborative for HSS with OPERAS-PLUS) • Sharla Lair (LYRASIS) • Kristi Holmes (DataCite/Make Data Count) • Christina Drummond (OAEBUDT) Group discussion
09:00-10:00	Working Session 1: FAIR , CARE, and usage data sharing
10:00-10:15	Break
10:15-11:10	Working Session 2: US-based public access usage reporting interoperability
11:10-12:00	Working Session 3: Facilitating cross-platform usage and impact analytics across scholarly output types
12:00-01:00	Lunch (provided on site)
01:00-02:10	Working Session 4: Developing recommendations for national infrastructure and investment
02:10-02:25	Break
02:25-03:45	Working Session 4 (continued): Developing recommendations for national infrastructure and investment
03:45-04:00	Wrap up

Workshop Participants

Organizing Committee: Charles Watkinson and Christina Drummond

Facilitator: Katherine Skinner

<i>Name</i>	<i>Title</i>	<i>Organization, Effort</i>
Charles Watkinson	Associate University Librarian	U-M Library
Chris Shillum	Executive Director	ORCID
Christina Drummond	Executive Director, OA Book Usage Data Trust	University of North Texas
Emily Farrell	Director of Open Research	Taylor and Francis / F1000
Joe Karaganis	Executive Director	Open Syllabus Project
John Lenahan	AVP Published Content	JSTOR
Katherine Klosek	Director, Information Policy	Association for Research Libraries (ARL)
Ken Klingenstein	Director, Middleware and Security Initiative	Internet2
Kristi Holmes	Make Data Count Advisory Board	DataCite / Make Data Count, Northwestern University
Laura Ricci	Senior Consultant	Clarke & Esposito
Lisa Hinchliffe	Professor	University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign
Martin Halbert	Program Officer	National Science Foundation
Maurice York	Director of Library Initiatives	Big Ten Academic Alliance
Mikala Narlock	Director	Data Curation Network
Niels Stern	Executive Director	OAPEN Foundation / Director of Open Access Books (DOAB)
Patricia Hswe	Program Officer	Mellon Foundation
Sharla Lair	Senior Strategist, OA and Scholarly Communications Initiatives	Lyrasis
Tina Baich	Visiting Program Officer	US Repository Network
Wendy Queen	Director	Project MUSE, Johns Hopkins University

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